

DIAGNOSIS OF THE SPIRITUAL AND MORAL QUALITIES OF THE CHARACTER AND THE SPIRITUAL FORMATION OF THE PERSON

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Abstract: *In this article it is analyzed the existing approaches to the understanding of spirituality, the inclusion of spirituality in the context of psychological analysis. The paper also views possible ways of spiritual and moral formation of a man.*

Key Words: *syntagma, moral, Moral character, moral formation, fairness, honesty, individual.*

There are numerous moral qualities which can be discussed but let us firstly focus on the first word from this syntagma – moral. If we look at Cambridge dictionary to help us define morality, here's what we'll find under the term 'moral': „relating to the standards of good or bad behaviour, fairness, honesty, etc. that each person believes in, rather than to laws.“ It is obvious that moral behaviour correlates to what we as human beings regard as „the right thing to do“ in agreement with our emotions and some generally shared moral principles of human behaviour. Therefore, moral qualities have nothing to do with law. For example, slavery was once legal (the law permitted its practice), but it is not morally „right“ nor acceptable. In short, moral qualities are those for which the possessor is the suitable recipient of the responsive attitudes. We can define morality and moral qualities as those tendencies of character for which it is appropriate to hold an individual morally responsible. A trait for which the individual is deserving of a positive responsive attitude, such as gratitude or praise, is a virtue, and a vice is a trait for which the individual is deserving of a negative responsive attitude, such as blame or resentment. Moral qualities are relatively fixed, stable and reliable dispositions of activity and affect which should be rationally informed.

Moral character is an analysis of an individual's steady moral qualities. The concept of *character* can express a variety of attributes including the presence or lack of virtues such as empathy, courage, fortitude, honesty, and loyalty, or of good behaviors

or habits, these attributes are also a part of one's soft skills. Moral character primarily refers to the collection of qualities that differentiate one individual from another – although on a cultural level, the group of moral behaviors to which a social group adheres can be said to unite and define it culturally as distinct from others. Psychologist Lawrence Pervin defines moral character as "a disposition to express behavior in consistent patterns of functions across a range of situations". Same as, the philosopher Marie I. George refers to moral character as the "sum of one's moral habits and dispositions". Aristotle has said, "we must take as a sign of states of character the pleasure or pain that ensues on acts.

In one experiment that was done in the United States in 1985, the moral character of a person was based on whether or not a person had found a dime in a public phone booth. The findings were that 87% of subjects who found a dime in a phone booth mailed a sealed and addressed envelope that was left at the booth in an apparent mistake by someone else, while only 4% of those who did not find a dime helped. Some found it very troubling that people would be influenced by such morally trivial factors in their choice whether to provide low-cost assistance to others. John M. Doris raises the issue of ecological validity – do experimental findings reflect phenomena found in natural contexts. He recognizes that these results are counterintuitive to the way most of us think about morally relevant behavior. Another experiment that was done that asked college students at Cornell to predict how they would behave when faced with one of several moral dilemmas, and to make the same predictions for their peers. Again and again, people predicted that they would be more generous and kind than others. Yet when put into the moral dilemma, the subjects did not behave as generously or as kindly as they had predicted. In psychological terms, the experimental subjects were successfully anticipating the base rate of moral behavior and accurately predicting how often others, in general, would be self-sacrificing.

On the basis of this understanding of moral formation, the ways in which people are morally formed can be further investigated. In *Formation of the moral self*, Johannes Van der Ven (1998) identifies and discusses seven teaching and learning processes of moral formation. He terms these modes of moral formation. He identifies two informal modes (discipline and socialisation) and five formal modes that can be found in educational institutions. The five formal modes are value clarification, emotional development, transmission, cognitive development and character formation. These modes involve knowing, being and doing which are

essential for a relational model of ethics. Value clarification, transmission and cognitive development all focus on the dimension of knowing. Van der Ven favours character formation which he considers to involve knowing, being and doing. In this discussion being and doing are seen as additional categories (not simply subsumed under 'character formation') because of their importance; moral formation takes place in a social and relational context.

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